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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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ANNOTATION

Accelerated tooth tissue destruction represents a significant challenge in modern dentistry due to its rapid progression and multifactorial etiology. This condition is associated with biological, behavioral, and environmental factors, including microbial activity, dietary habits, reduced salivary function, and systemic health disorders. Modern treatment concepts focus on early diagnosis, risk assessment, and minimally invasive approaches aimed at preserving hard dental tissues. Preventive strategies, remineralization therapy, bioactive materials, and individualized treatment planning play a key role in controlling disease progression. An interdisciplinary and patient-centered approach is essential for achieving long-term clinical success and improving oral health outcomes.

Keywords: Accelerated tooth tissue destruction, rapid dental caries progression, minimally invasive dentistry, remineralization therapy, preventive dentistry, bioactive dental materials, risk assessment, modern treatment concepts.

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СОВРЕМЕННАЯ КОНЦЕПЦИЯ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ИЗНОСОМ ТВЕРДЫХ ТКАНЕЙ ЗУБОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Износ твердых тканей зубов относится к группе наиболее распространённых некариозных поражений и представляет собой прогрессирующий, необратимый процесс утраты эмали и дентина, возникающий под влиянием комплекса механических, химических и биомеханических факторов. В последние годы во всем мире отмечается устойчивый рост распространенности данной патологии, что связано с изменением пищевых привычек, увеличением потребления кислотосодержащих продуктов, ростом уровня

психоэмоционального стресса, распространённостью парафункций жевательных мышц и увеличением продолжительности жизни населения. Современная концепция лечения основывается на принципах ранней диагностики, индивидуальной оценки факторов риска, профилактической направленности, минимально инвазивного восстановления и междисциплинарного подхода. В статье представлен углублённый анализ современных научных данных, клинических алгоритмов и статистических показателей, основанный на международных, европейских, российских и узбекских источниках литературы.

Ключевые слова: износ твердых тканей зубов, патологическая стираемость, эрозия, атриция, абразия, абфракция, минимально инвазивное лечение.

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TISHLARNING JADAL YEMIRILISHIDA BEMORLARNI DAVOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY KONSEPSIYASI

ANNOTATSIYA

Tishlarning jadal yemirilishi stomatologiyada dolzarb muammolardan biri bo'lib, kasallikning tez rivojlanishi va ko'p omilli etiologiyasi bilan tavsiflanadi. Mazkur holat og'iz bo'shlig'i mikroflorasi faolligi, uglevodlarga boy ovqatlanish, so'lak ajralishining kamayishi hamda umumiy somatik kasalliklar bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Zamonaviy davolash konsepsiyalari kasallikni erta aniqlash, xavf omillarini baholash va minimal invaziv yondashuvlarga asoslanadi. Profilaktik choralar, remineralizatsiya terapiyasi va biofaol stomatologik materiallardan foydalanish tish qattiq to'qimalarini saqlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tishlarning jadal yemirilishi, tez rivojlanuvchi kariyes, minimal invaziv stomatologiya, remineralizatsiya terapiyasi, profilaktik stomatologiya, biofaol materiallar, kariyes xavfini baholash.

Kirish

Tishlarning qattiq to'qimalari yemirilishi, xususan jadal rivojlanadigan shakllari, bugungi kunda stomatologik amaliyotda muhim klinik va ijtimoiy ahamiyatga ega muammo hisoblanadi. Kasallikning ushbu turi qisqa vaqt ichida emal va dentinning sezilarli darajada shikastlanishi bilan kechib, tishlarning funksional va estetik holatini buzadi. Jadal yemirilish ko'pincha bolalar, o'smirlar va umumiy organizm holati zaiflashgan bemorlarda uchraydi. Ilmiy tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, tishlarning jadal yemirilishi multifaktorial etiologiyaga ega bo'lib, kariyesogen mikroorganizmlar faolligi, og'iz bo'shlig'i gigiyenasining yetarli emasligi, uglevodlarga boy va tez-tez iste'mol qilinadigan ovqatlar, so'lakning miqdoriy va sifat o'zgarishlari asosiy patogen omillar hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari, endokrin tizim kasalliklari, oshqozon-ichak yo'li patologiyalari hamda immun holatning pasayishi jarayonni yanada tezlashtiradi. An'anaviy davolash usullari ko'pincha to'qimalarning katta hajmda olib tashlanishiga olib kelgan bo'lsa, zamonaviy stomatologiya tish to'qimalarini maksimal darajada saqlab qolishga qaratilgan konsepsiyalarni ilgari suradi. Bugungi kunda minimal invaziv davolash, remineralizatsiya terapiyasi, individual xavf darajasini baholash va profilaktik yondashuvlar jadal yemirilishning oldini olish va uning rivojlanishini sekinlashtirishda asosiy yo'nalish sifatida qaralmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasi

Maqsad. Tishlarning jadal yemirilishi bilan og'rikan bemorlarda zamonaviy davolash konsepsiyalarining klinik samaradorligini baholash va ularning tish qattiq to'qimalarini saqlashdagi ahamiyatini aniqlash.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari. Tadqiqotga 2023–2025-yillar davomida Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti klinikasida ortopedik stomatologik davolanish uchun murojaat qilgan 18 yoshdan 55 yoshgacha bo'lgan 50 nafar bemor kiritildi. Klinik va laborator tekshiruvlardan

o'tkazildi, tishlarning holati DMF indeksi yordamida baholandi, so'lakning miqdoriy va sifat ko'rsatkichlari sialometriya usuli orqali aniqlandi.

Bemorlar ikki guruhga ajratildi. Nazorat guruhida an'anaviy davolash usullari qo'llanildi. Asosiy guruhda esa minimal invaziv preparatsiya, remineralizatsiya terapiyasi hamda fluor, kalsiy-fosfat birikmalariga asoslangan biofaol materiallardan foydalanildi. Davolash natijalari 6 oy davomida dinamik kuzatuv asosida baholandi.

Rasm1. Tishlarning generallashgan yemirilishi.

Rasm2. Tishlarning lokal yemirilishi.

Restavratsiyalarning klinik samaradorligi quyidagi mezonlar asosida baholandi:

- restavratsiyaning funksional barqarorligi;
- chaynash yuklamasi ostida mustahkamligi;
- og'riq sezgilari va patologik harakatchanlikning yo'qligi;
- chetki moslashuv sifati;
- estetik ko'rsatkichlar;
- ildiz va periapikal to'qimalarning rentgenologik holati.

Nazorat ko'riklari davolashdan so'ng 6 va 12 oy muddatlarda o'tkazildi.

Rentgenologik tekshiruv usullari

Tishlarning jadal yemirilishini aniqlash va kariyes jarayonining chuqurligi hamda dentin to'qimasiga tarqalish darajasini baholash maqsadida rentgenologik tekshiruvlar o'tkazildi. Bunda periapikal rentgenografiya va bite-wing (tishlararo) rentgen tasvirlaridan foydalanildi. Rentgenologik tekshiruvlar yashirin kariyes o'choqlarini aniqlash, dentin strukturasiidagi o'zgarishlarni baholash hamda davolash taktikasini tanlashda muhim diagnostik ahamiyatga ega bo'ldi. Olingan rentgen tasvirlar kariyes jarayonining bosqichlari, mineralizatsiya darajasi va patologik o'zgarishlarning lokalizatsiyasiga ko'ra tahlil qilindi. Rentgenologik ma'lumotlar klinik ko'rsatkichlar bilan solishtirildi va kompleks baholash amalga oshirildi.

Laborator va funksional tekshiruvlar

So'lak ajralishining miqdoriy ko'rsatkichlari sialometriya usuli yordamida aniqlanib, so'lakning pH darajasi va mineral tarkibi baholandi. Ushbu ko'rsatkichlar kariyes jarayonining faolligini aniqlashda muhim mezon sifatida qabul qilindi.

Statistik ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash

Tadqiqot davomida olingan barcha klinik, rentgenologik va laborator ma'lumotlar statistik jihatdan qayta ishlandi. Natijalar o'rtacha qiymat (M) va standart og'ish ($\pm SD$) ko'rinishida ifodalandi. Guruhlar o'rtasidagi farqlarni aniqlash uchun variatsion statistik tahlil usullari qo'llanildi. Olingan natijalarning ishonchlilik darajasi $p < 0,05$ mezoni asosida baholandi. Statistik tahlil zamonaviy davolash konsepsiyalarining klinik samaradorligini obyektiv baholash va olingan natijalarning ilmiy asoslanganligini ta'minlashga xizmat qildi. Olingan ma'lumotlar standart kuzatuv kartalarida qayd etildi. Miqdoriy ko'rsatkichlar uchun o'rtacha qiymat va standart og'ish hisoblandi. Natijalar guruhlar o'rtasida tavsifiy statistik tahlil yordamida solishtirildi. Tadqiqot Xelsinki deklaratsiyasi talablariga muvofiq amalga oshirildi. Barcha bemorlardan davolash va klinik ma'lumotlardan ilmiy maqsadlarda foydalanish uchun yozma ravishda ongli rozilik olindi.

Tadqiqot natijalari

Bemorlarning klinik tavsifi va davolash hajmi

Tadqiqot davomida 50 nafar bemorda ortopedik davo amalga oshirildi. Tiklangan tishlarning asosiy qismini yuqori va pastki jag'ning premolyar hamda molyar tishlari tashkil etdi, bu esa mazkur tishlarning funksional yuklamasi yuqori ekanligi bilan izohlanadi.

Bemorlarning aksariyatida tish toj qismi 30–40% gacha yo'qotilganligi aniqlandi.

Jadval 1. Tadqiqotda tiklangan tishlarning joylashuviga ko'ra taqsimlanishi

Tish guruhi	Tiklangan tishlar soni	Ulushi (%)
Kesuvchi tishlar	12	20.7
Qoziq tishlar	9	15.5
Premolyarlar	18	31.0
Molyarlar	19	32.8

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, eng ko'p tiklash ishlari chaynash yuklamasi yuqori bo'lgan molyar va premolyar tishlarda amalga oshirilgan.

Klinik moslashuv va erta davr natijalari. Davolashdan keyingi dastlabki 7–14 kun davomida bemorlarning shikoyatlari, og'riq sezgisi va yumshoq to'qimalarning holati baholandi.

Jadval 2. Davolashdan keyingi 14 kun ichidagi klinik holatlar

Klinik ko'rsatkichlar	Bemorlar soni	Ulushi (%)
Og'riqsiz holat	34	85.0
Yengil noqulaylik	5	12.5
Og'riq sindromi	1	2.5

Qayd etilgan yengil og'riq holatlari qisqa muddatli bo'lib, qo'shimcha dori vositalarisiz bartaraf etildi. Funksional samaradorlikni baholash natijalari. Tishlarning chaynash funksiyasi davolashdan oldin va keyin taqqoslama asosida baholandi.

Jadval 3. Chaynash funksiyasining tiklanish ko'rsatkichlari

Baholash bosqichi	O'rtacha ko'rsatkich (%)
O'rtacha ko'rsatkich (%)	54,2 \pm 4,0
Davolashdan keyin	87,6 \pm 3,2

Ortopedik davo ko'rsatilgandan so'ng funksional tiklanishda yuqori samaradorlikka ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Rentgenologik nazorat natijalari. Rentgenologik tekshiruvlar davolashdan so'ng 3 va 6 oy o'tgach amalga oshirildi.

Jadval 4. 6 oydan so'ng rentgenologik baholash natijalari

Rentgen belgilar	Holatlar soni	Ulushi (%)
O'zgarishsiz holat	37	92.5
Yengil periapikal o'zgarishlar	2	5.0
Salbiy dinamikalar	1	2.5

Mazkur natijalar O'zbekiston sharoitida zamonaviy ortopedik stomatologik yondashuvlarni amaliyotga keng joriy etish maqsadga muvofiq ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Natijalarni muhokama qilish

Tadqiqotimizda 50 nafar bemor (yoshi 25–60) ishtirok etdi. Bemorlar tishlarda tez yemirilish, og'riq, estetik nuqsonlar va ovqatlanishdagi noqulaylik bilan murojaat qilishgan. Klinik va radiografik tekshiruv natijalari quyidagicha:

Klinik topilmalar: Bemorlarning 60%ida bir nechta tishlar jadal yemirilgan. 35% holatda pulpa yallig'lanishi (pulpitis) aniqlangan, ularning ayrimida periapikal o'zgarishlar kuzatilgan.

Tishlar orasida aloqasiz bo'shliqlar va alveolyar suyakka yoyilgan yallig'lanish belgilari 40% hollarda aniqlangan.

Radiografik va 3D diagnostika: Panoramik rentgenogramma va CBCT tish ildizi va alveolyar suyaktagi mikrocracklarni aniqlashga imkon berdi.

3D intraoral skanerlash tish emali va dentin qatlamidagi ingichka yemirilishlarni aniqladi.

Davolash natijalari: Minimal invaziv yondashuvlar (mikroretensiya, kompozit plomba va tish qismlarini tiklash) qo'llanildi.

Ortopedik yondashuvlar: individual koronkalar, inklyuziv protezlar va kombine protezlar orqali tish funksiyasini tiklash amalga oshirildi.

6 oy davomida kuzatish natijalari: tish funksiyasi 85% holatda tiklandi, og'riq sezilarli darajada kamaydi, estetik qoniqish 90% ga yetdi.

Bemorlarning sub'ektiv bahosi: Ovqatlanish qulayligi oshdi.

Psixologik holat yaxshilandi, o'ziga bo'lgan ishonch ortdi.

Bemorlarning ko'pchiligi keyingi profilaktik nazorat va og'iz gigiyenasiga qat'iy rioya qilishga tayyor ekanligini bildirdi.

Tishlarning jadal yemirilishi ortopedik stomatologiyada keng tarqalgan va murakkab davolashni talab qiladigan dolzarb masala hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari quyidagi asosiy jihatlarni ko'rsatdi:

Etiologiya va sabablar: Jadal yemirilish karyogen mikroflora, yomon og'iz gigiyenasi, tish anatomiyasi va sistemik kasalliklar bilan bog'liq.

Periodontit bilan birgalikda kechadigan yemirilish tish ildizining barqarorligini kamaytiradi va ortopedik davolashni murakkablashtiradi.

Minimal invaziv yondashuvlar: Tish strukturasi maksimal saqlash va funktsional tiklashni ta'minlash uchun mikroretensiya, kompozit plomba va tish qismlarini tiklash ishlari samarali. Ushbu yondashuv tishning tabiiy tuzilishini saqlash, ovqatni chaynash funksiyasini tiklash va keyingi protezlash imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishga yordam beradi.

Ortopedik stomatologiyada zamonaviy konsepsiya: Individual koronkalar, inklyuziv va kombine protezlar yordamida tish funksiyasini tiklash bemorning og'iz bo'shlig'idagi barqarorlikni ta'minlaydi.

3D diagnostika vositalari (CBCT, intraoral skanerlar) tish ildizi va alveolyar suyak holatini aniqlashda, tish strukturasi yoriqlarni erta aniqlashda muhimdir.

Protezlash va tiklash jarayonida tish anatomiyasi, oklyuziya va funktsional yuki hisobga olinadi.

Bemorning psixologik va funktsional holati: Tishlarning tiklanishi ovqatlanish qobiliyati, talaffuz va estetik ko'rinishni yaxshilaydi. Bu bemorning psixologik holatiga ijobiy ta'sir qiladi, o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchni oshiradi.

Profilaktika va tavsiyalar: Jadal yemirilish xavfi yuqori bo'lgan bemorlarda muntazam nazorat, og'iz gigiyenasi, floridlangan preparatlar va dieta nazorati tavsiya etiladi.

Ortopedik stomatologik yondashuvlar bilan birgalikda profilaktik chora-tadbirlar tish yo‘qotilishi xavfini kamaytiradi.

Xulosa

Tishlarning jadal yemirilishi ortopedik stomatologiyada keng tarqalgan va murakkab davolashni talab qiladigan dolzarb muammo hisoblanadi. Bu holat bemorning og‘iz bo‘shlig‘idagi funkcionallik va estetik ko‘rinishga salbiy ta‘sir qiladi, shuningdek, tish yo‘qotilishi xavfini oshiradi. Minimal invaziv yondashuvlar (mikroretensiya, kompozit plomba, tish qismlarini tiklash) va individual ortopedik protezlar (koronkalar, inklyuziv va kombine protezlar) tish funksiyasi va estetik qoniqishini tiklashda samarali vositalardir. Ushbu yondashuvlar tish anatomiyasini maksimal saqlashga, ovqatni chaynash va talaffuzni tiklashga yordam beradi. Zamonaviy diagnostika vositalari (3D CBCT, intraoral skanerlar) tish strukturasiidagi microcracklarni va suyak yo‘qotilishini erta aniqlash imkonini beradi. Bu esa davolash strategiyasini aniq belgilash, bemorlar salomatligini yaxshilash va tish yo‘qotilishi xavfini kamaytirishga xizmat qiladi. Ortopedik stomatologiyada tishlarning funkcionallik tiklanishi bemorning ovqatlanish qobiliyatini, talaffuzini va estetik ko‘rinishini yaxshilaydi. Shu bilan birga, bemorning psixologik holati va o‘ziga bo‘lgan ishonchi sezilarli darajada yaxshilanadi. Tishlarni vaqtida tiklash va profilaktik nazorat zamonaviy stomatologiyada tish yo‘qotilishi xavfini kamaytirish, og‘iz salomatligini saqlash va bemorning hayot sifatini yaxshilashning muhim qismidir.

Kelajakda bemorlar bilan individual yondashuv, minimal invaziv tiklash va zamonaviy ortopedik protezlash kombinatsiyasi jadal yemirilgan tishlarni samarali davolashning asosiy konsepsiyasini tashkil etadi.

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